

Comparative Analysis between Open Defecation Practices and Environmental Health Status on Residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State

Waliu Babatunde Ogunbamowo¹

waliu.ogunbamowo@lasu.edu.ng

08023439881

Bidemi Bilkis Lafiaji-Okuneye¹

bbidowu2000@yahoo.com

08028611198

Habeeb Ladi OWOLABI²

hablad@yahoo.com

08138456825

¹Department of Human Kinetics, Sports and Health Education, Faculty of Education Lagos State University, Ojo

²Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Lagos State University of Education, Oto-Ijanikin

Abstract

The study examined the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Two research questions and hypotheses were postulated and it employed descriptive research design. The Population of this study consists of all residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Simple Random sampling techniques was adopted and sample for this study was Three hundred (300) residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The research instrument for this study was a self-developed modified Questionnaire, titled Environmental Open Defecation Questionnaire (EODHQ). The Test-retest method of reliability was adopted, the reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha technique of r value= 0.86. Data collected was analyzed using frequency count and percentages for data representation while inferential statistics of Chi-square and Linear regression was used to test all stated hypotheses. The finding revealed that, there was significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State and Attitude of residents have significant relationship with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State and it was recommend that government should ensure the construction of more decent public latrine facilities in the area to end open defecation.

Keywords: Attitude of Residents, Open Defecation and Health of Residents

Introduction

The health of individuals remains largely unmet and often side-lined in circumstances where open defecation is available. Open defecation is defined as the practice of defecating in open fields, waterways and open trenches without any proper disposal of human excreta (Belay, et al, 2022). Open defecation is strongly associated with incidence of diarrhea disease, prevalence of helminthic infection and stunting especially in children less than five years of age. Open defecation is the human practice of defecating outside ("in the open") rather than into a toilet. People may choose fields, bushes, forests, ditches, streets, canals, or other open spaces for defecation. They do so either because they do not have a toilet readily accessible or due to traditional cultural practices (Clasen, 2014).

Open defecation is credited to the publications of Joint Monitoring Program (JMP) in 2008, a joint collaboration of World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations International Children Emergency Fund (UNICEF) to evaluate the global progress on water and sanitation goals. Open defecation is classified as unimproved sanitation (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Despite 15 years of conjunctive efforts under global action plans such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), targets for improved sanitation were not met, resulting in 2.5 billion people not having access to improved sanitation facilities (flush latrine or pit latrine) and nearly 892 million of the total world's population still practice open defecation (Bisung & Elliot, 2016). As a result of this failure to successfully ensure basic sanitation it was once again highlighted as a key issue in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Number 6 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is to "Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all", where the Target aims by 2030 is to achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations (United Nations, 2015).

In 2020, 54% of the global population (4.2 billion people) used a safely managed sanitation service; 34% (2.6 billion people) used private sanitation facilities connected to sewers from which wastewater was treated; 20% (1.6 billion people) used toilets or latrines where excreta were safely disposed and 78% of the world population (6.1 billion people) used at least a basic sanitation service (WHO, 2015). The average proportion of ‘open defecators’ in developing countries is 16%, and in the least-developed countries 20%. Of those who still practice open defecation 90% of people reside in rural areas of three regions; sub-Saharan Africa, Central Asia and Southern Asia (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Diarrhoea remains a major killer but is largely preventable. Better water, sanitation, and hygiene could prevent the deaths of 297 000 children aged under 5 years each year. Open defecation perpetuates a vicious cycle of disease and poverty. The countries where open defecation is most widespread have the highest number of deaths of children aged less than 5 years as well as the highest levels of malnutrition and poverty, and big disparities of wealth (WHO, 2022).

Nigeria (located in West Africa) is among the countries with the highest rate of open defecation ranking 2nd in Africa and 5th globally in 2010 (WHO & UNICEF, 2012). A report by Abubakar, (2008) highlighted that in 2015 about 46 million Nigerians engaged in outdoor defecation, bringing Nigeria from 5th position to 3rd position in prevalence of open defecation globally. According to WHO/UNICEF, (2012) reported that 34 million Nigerians practiced open defecation in 2010. The World Development Indicators in 2016 also confirmed that open defecation practice in Nigeria had risen from 24% to 25.1% of its population in 1990 to 2015 respectively (World Bank & World Development Indicators, 2016). October 2019, The Nigeria Minister, Suleiman Adamu of Ministry of Water Resources in a forum on sanitation organized by Organised Private Sector, disclosed that Nigeria now ranks 1st in the world in open defecation prevalence with about 50 million Nigerians practicing open defecation. This indicates that open defecation is a burden in Nigeria. Open defecation leads to outbreak of infections which the government needs to contain to prevent loss of lives. The World Bank estimated that about \$8.3 billion will be needed by the Nigerian federal government to curb open defecation (World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2015).

Open defecation can pollute the environment and cause health problems and diseases. High levels of open defecation are linked to high child mortality, poor nutrition, poverty, and large disparities between rich and poor (World Health Organization & United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2014). In ancient times, there were more open spaces and less population pressure on land. It was believed that defecating in the open causes little harm when done in areas with low population, forests, or camping-type situations. With development and urbanization, open defecating started becoming a challenge and thereby an important public health issue, and an issue of human dignity (O'Reilly, 2016) With the increase in population in smaller areas, such as cities and towns, more attention was given to hygiene and health. As a result, there was an increase in global attention towards reducing the practice of open defecation. Open defecation perpetuates the vicious cycle of disease and poverty and is widely regarded as an affront to personal dignity. The countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of under nutrition, high levels of poverty, and large disparities between the rich and poor (WHO & UNICEF, 2014).

The negative public health impacts of open defecation are the same as those described when there is no access to sanitation at all (Desai, McFarlane & Graham, 2015). Such impacts include, but not limited to, environmental pollution due to widespread scattering of human feces even in public utilities, loss of income and productive time including missed school hours and days by school-aged children, and finally lack of privacy, dignity, and threat to human safety (Desai, et al., 2015). Open defecation and lack of sanitation and hygiene in general is an important factor that cause various diseases, the most common being diarrhea and intestinal worm infections but also typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma, and others (Spears, & Haddad, 2015). Adverse Health effects of open defecation occur because opens defecation results in fecal contamination of the local environment. Consequently, open defecators are repeatedly exposed to many kinds of fecal bacteria like gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and other fecal pathogens, and this is particularly serious for young children whose immune systems and brains are not yet fully developed. Certain diseases are grouped together under the name of waterborne diseases, which are diseases transmitted via fecal pathogens in water. Open defecation can lead to water pollution when rain flushes feces that are dispersed in the environment into surface water or unprotected wells (Anoop, et al, 2020).

Those countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of malnourishment (leading to stunted growth in children), high levels of poverty, and large disparities between rich and poor (WHO & UNICEF, 2017). Infected human excreta contain several harmful organisms that are associated with a number of health problems. Virtually, one gram of infected human excreta can contain a variety of microbes which includes 106 pathogenic viruses and viral infections, 106-108 bacterial pathogens, 103 protozoan cysts and 10-104 helminth eggs (Belcher, 2018). Inappropriate human waste disposal also increases the risk of exposure to these pathogens which can pose significant health risks such as transferable infectious diseases, diarrhoea, typhoid and cholera, and

viral infections (Pruss-Ustun, et al, 2008). The unpleasant and continuing environmental effects encountered by residents are becoming disturbing and their health is in great chaos with this method of disposing excreta especially the health of their children (Ogunbamowo, Ashon & Elemoro-Oni, 2022). Environmental pollution encountered by residents include; increase in waterborne diseases which can cause diarrhea, cholera, trachoma; increase in vector diseases. Children are the most vulnerable to environmental pollutants. This is because they are not aware of their activities and their surroundings, and also they do not have adequate knowledge of health implication of environmental and air pollution escaping is so difficult for them. More so, the fact that children find it easy to play anywhere and in any condition they find themselves exposes them more to the danger of air pollution.

Open defecation and lack of sanitation and hygiene in general is an important factor that cause various diseases, the most common being diarrhea and intestinal worm infections but also typhoid, cholera, hepatitis. Most children get malnourished from the disposal of this waste in the area. It is sad that most of the residents have been found not to recognize the effects of open defecation until signs and symptoms of health impairment manifest and even if they do recognize it, poor knowledge has allowed them. The stench and foul smell in the area is another probing menace from the use of open defecation. Therefore, this study assesses the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the Comparative analysis between Open defecation practices and Environmental health status on residents in mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Other specific purposes were:

1. To examine the practices of open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To examine the Attitude of residents towards open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do the practices of open defecation exist among the residents among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. To what extent does the attitude of residents affect the practice of open defecation among the residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were postulated for the study:

1. There will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. There will be no significant relationship between the attitude of residents and the practice of open Defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted for this study while the Population of this study consists of all residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. Simple Random sampling techniques was adopted for this study and sample for this study was Three hundred (300) residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The research instrument for this study was a self-developed modified Questionnaire, titled Environmental Open Defecation Questionnaire (EODHQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections: A and B, Section A contained demographic data of respondents, while section B was an opinion question on environmental Effect of open defecation on the health of all residents. The questionnaire adopted a four (4) point Likert scale as stated: Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D). The content, construct and face validity of the questionnaire were ascertained in the Department of Human Kinetics, Sports and Health Education, Lagos State University, Ojo, by panel of three experts including researchers supervisor to ensure a thoroughness which indicated that the instrument measured what it was intended to measure in relation to research questions and hypotheses. The Test-retest method of reliability was adopted. This required the researcher to administer twenty (10) copies of the validated questionnaire to twenty (10) participants from Lagos Island Local Government Area to determine the reliability of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha technique of r value= 0.86 which was very good.

The copies of questionnaire were personally distributed with the help of three trained research assistants to the respondents. Three hundred (300) questionnaires were distributed and collected by the researcher at the spot and data collected lasted for four (4) weeks among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Copies of the administered questionnaire were checked to ensure that they were well completed before leaving the study area. The researcher monitored the process of data collection throughout. Daily review meeting were held at the beginning and end of each day with the research assistants. Data collected was analyzed using appropriate descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages for data representation while inferential statistics of Chi-square and Linear regression was used to test all stated hypotheses at 0.05 level alpha of significance. The statistical package for social science (SPSS) was used for analyzing the data collected.

Presentation of Results

Demographic Analysis

Table: 1 Distribution of respondents by Age, Gender, Tribe, Marital Status and Accommodation type.

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
21-30	234	78.0
31-40	31	10.3
41-50	23	7.7
50 years above	12	4.0
Total	300	100.0

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	37	12.3
Female	263	87.7
Total	300	100

Tribe	Frequency	Percentage %
Yoruba	133	44.3
Igbo	1	0.3
Hausa	166	55.3
Others	0	0
Total	300	100.0

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage %
Non-Formal	248	82.7
Primary	26	5.6
Secondary	17	8.7
Tertiary	9	3.0
Total	300	100.0

Accommodation type	Frequency	Percentage %
Uncompleted	85	28.3
Boys Quarter	6	2.0
A Room	199	66.3
Flat	10	3.4
Total	300	100.0

Table 1 Demographic on Age showed that 234 (78.0%) of the respondents were within the age bracket of 21-30 year, while 31 (10.3%) were within the age bracket of 31-40 years and 23 (7.7%) were 41-50 years, and 12 (4.0%) were within the age bracket of 50 years above. Consecutively the demographic on Gender showed that 37 (12.3%) of the respondents were male while 263 (87.7%) of the respondents were female. The demographic on Tribe showed that 133 (44.3%) of the respondents were Yoruba, while 1 (0.3%) were Igbo, 166 (55.3%) were Hausa while 0% was recorded for other tribe. The demographic on Marital Status showed that 248 (82.7%) of the respondents had Non-formal education, while 26 (5.6%) had primary education, 17 (8.7%) had secondary education and 9 (3.0%) had Tertiary education. Finally the demographic on Accommodation type showed that 85

(28.3%) of the respondents lived in uncompleted building, while 6 (2.0%) lived in boys quarter, 199 (66.3%) lived in a room and 10 (3.4%) lived in Flat.

Hypothesis One

Hypothesis one states that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. This hypothesis was tested using Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented on the table 2 below.

Table: 2 Chi-square (X^2) results on Practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual X^2	Sig
Strongly agree	54	99.7	-33.7	95.445
Agree	179	99.7	79.3	
Disagree	66	99.7	-45.7	
Strongly Disagree	0			
Total	300			0.000

From the result presented on table 4.6 above, it could be observed that a significant Chi-square value ($X^2=95.445$, $p<0.05$) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance, therefore hypothesis one as stated is hereby rejected. This implies that there was significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The distribution of respondents' responses showed that majority (179) agreed to have practiced followed by 54 respondents that strongly agreed, 66 respondents disagreed while just 0 respondents strongly disagreed.

Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis one states that there will be no significant relationship between attitude of residents and the practice of open defecation among residents in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. The result is presented on the table below.

Table: 3 linear regression result on relationship between attitude of resident and practice of Open defecation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	SE	Beta			
R = 0.023						
R ² = 0.001						
AR ² = -.003						
F = .163						
Sig. = 0.013*						
Model (Constant)	3.091	0.326			9.481	0.000
Regular exercise	-.045	0.112	-.023		-.404	0.013

Dependent Variable: Practice of Open defecation

It could be observed from table 4.7 above that the relationship between regular exercise and occurrence of blood pressure could be predicted at 2.3% ($R^2=0.023$) accuracy. The table further showed that a significant F-value ($F=.163$; $P=0.013$) was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, hypothesis two as stated above is hereby rejected. This implies that Attitude of residents had significant relationship with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State. The positive t-value ($t=9.4881$; $P<0.05$) implies that Attitude of residents have a significant relationship with the practice of Open defecation among residents of Mainland Local government Area, Lagos State.

Discussion

The Hypothesis one above states that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State. This finding is supported by a study on open defecation practice and its determinants among households in sub-Saharan Africa, pooled prevalence and multilevel analysis of 33 sub-Sahara Africa countries demographic and health survey by Belay, Asratie & Aragaw, (2022) agreeing that Open defecation is more practice in sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. A total of thirty-three SSA countries were represented for this study in the four regions of the total of 47 countries located in SSA, only 41 countries had Demographic and Health Survey reports. All households

which were found across 33 SSA countries during the survey period were the source population. Whereas households assessed for sanitation facilities during each survey across 33 SSA countries were the study population. The analysis contained a total weighted sample of 452,281 households. Demographic and Health Survey data sets of 33 SSA countries with a total sample of 452,281 households were used for this study. The pooled prevalence of open defecation practice among households in sub-Saharan African countries was 22.55%. It was concluded that open defecation practice remains a public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa.

Another study was in agreement by Coffey, et al., (2014) lamented the high rate in the practice of open defecation in rural communities which remains stubbornly widespread with several dire consequences affecting the human health and environment alike. This barbaric practice kills babies, and impedes the physical and cognitive development of surviving children. It also has significant negative externalities and releases germs into the environment which pose serious harm to both the rich and the poor in the society. Open defecation is very common, even in households with access to a latrine and Communicable diseases outbreak was a threat not only to lives of individuals but also national security (Ogunbamowo & Oladipupo-Okorie, 2021). In four focus states, 80% of all interviewed households had at least one member who defecates in the open. Forty-eight per cent of households with a working latrine which are determined either by the fact that someone in the household used it or by the presence of a pit and seat, had at least one member who nevertheless defecates in the open. Strikingly, in the four focus states, 45% of households with a latrine user also had at least one household member who defecates in the open. In another study which agreed with the findings by Belcher, (2018), poor latrine conditions, structure, and design may deter latrine use and provoke reversion to open defecation. Statistics show that only 18% of the households in Turkana County, Kenya, have access to a latrine facility with most of these facilities in poor structural designs and poor hygienic conditions, which encourages rampant open defecation practices. It would therefore be inferred that there will be no significant practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area.

The Hypothesis Two above states that "There will be no significant relationship between attitudes with the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State". The finding agrees with a study by Board & Suzuki, (2015) a survey was conducted in Ojo Local Government Area. Five areas were randomly selected from this area for the study with 281 heads of each household filled the questionnaire. The attitude of respondents in the Local Government Area was negative. Open defecation was higher among households that did not have latrine. In another study which agrees with the findings by Bakobie, et al., (2021) assessed the attitudes of each household in a community in Indonesia. The sample consisted of 92 heads of families who live in Cibaduyut Village, and the sampling technique used was stratified random sampling. Data were collected by means of interviews and a questionnaire. Attitude variable is 0.855, it is 85.5% variance of the attitude variable which can be explained by the formed factors, and finally the Social Interaction Variable is 0.848. The relationship between Attitude and open defecation behavior in Nagari Koto Rawang, IV Jurai, Pesisir Selatan Regency, which agrees with the study by Anoop, et al, (2020). From the results of the data analysis, it was found out that from the 50 respondents who open defecation, 64.0% of them have poor attitudes, and 63.0% of respondents who had good attitudes, defecated in the latrine. Based on bivariate analysis result with the Chi-square test on the Attitude variable with open defecation behavior obtained p-value = 0.021 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, it shows that the attitudes had a significant relationship with open defecation behavior. Therefore, it could be inferred that there is significant relationship between attitudes of residents with the practice of open defecation in Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was inferred that;

1. There was significant widespread of sanitation practices of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.
2. There was significant relationship between attitude of residents and the practice of open defecation among residents of Mainland Local Government Area, Lagos State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The landlords should be given a must task to ensure they have latrine facilities in every rentals.
2. The government should ensure the construction of more decent public latrine facilities in the area to end open defecation.
3. The cost of using public toilet facilities should be at a subsidized price where everyone can afford to pay to use it and the usage should be free for the aged and children.

4. The government with the help of Non-governmental organization should create more awareness, sensitization, education of the community on proper sanitation management especially on latrine facilities and its consequences of open defecation.

References

- Anoop, J., Ashley, W., Claire, S. & Isha, R., (2020). Environmental consequences of open defecation. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. (4): 1384. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17041384.
- Bakobie, N., Abdul-Raheem, I.T., & Duwiejuah, A., (2021). Sanitation Practices and Microbial quality of drinking water in open defecation free and open defaecation communities in the Savelugu Municipality. *Ghana Journal of Science*. 61 (2), 1-12. doi:10.4314/gjs.v61i2.1
- Belay, D. G., Asratie, M. H. & Aragaw, F. M. (2022). Open defecation practice and its determinants among households in sub-Saharan Africa: pooled prevalence and multilevel analysis of 33 sub-Saharan Africa countries demographic and health survey. *Trop Med Health* 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41182-022-00416-5>.
- Belcher, J.B. (2018). Sanitation norms in rural areas: a cross-cultural comparison, *Bulletin of Pan American Health Organization*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 34–44,
- Bisung, E. & Elliott S. J. (2016). 'Everyone is exhausted and frustrated': Exploring psychosocial impacts of the lack of access to safe water and adequate sanitation in Usoma, Kenya. *J. Water Sanit. Hyg. Dev.*;6:205–214. doi: 10.2166/washdev.122.
- Board, A. R. & Suzuki, S. (2015). The interrelation between intestinal parasites and latent TB infections among newly resettled refugees in Texas. *Int. Health* 8 (1), 67–72
- Clasen, T., Boisson, S., Routray, P., Torondel, B., Bell M. & Cumming, O. (2014) "Effectiveness of a rural sanitation program on diarrhea, soil-transmitted helminth infection, and child malnutrition in Odisha, India: a cluster-randomized trial". *The Lancet. Global Health*. 2 (11): e645-53. doi:10.1016/S2214-109X(14)70307-9.
- Coffey, D. & Geruso, M. & Spears, D. (2016). Sanitation, Disease, and Anemia: Evidence From 5Nepal. *College of Liberal Arts, University of Texas at Austin, Austin, TX*. Available from: <https://laits.utexas.edu/~mlg2296/images/SanitationAnemia.pdf>.
- Desai, R., McFarlane, C. & Graham, S., (2015). The politics of open defecation: informality, body, and infrastructure in Mumbai. *Antipode*.47:98-120.
- Ogunbamowo, W. B., Ashon, D. O. & Elemoro-Oni, A. A. (2022). The Perceived Effect of Early Exposure to Environmental Pollution on Development of Childhood Diseases Among Residents of Rural Communities in Lagos State. *Journal of Human Kinetics and Health Education Pedagogy*. 4 (1), 74-84.
- Ogunbamowo, W. B. & Oladipupo, B. O. (2021). Assessment of the Role of Primary Health Care Strategies in Preventing Childhood diseases in Nigerian Air Force Medical Services in Lagos State. *Journal of Research and Contemporary issues in Human Kinetics and Health Education*, 6 (1), 91-99.
- O'Reilly K. (2016). "From toilet insecurity to toilet security: creating safe sanitation for women and girls". *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water*. 3 (1): 19–24. doi:10.1002/wat2.1122. ISSN 2049-1948. S2CID 109965522.
- Prüss-Üstün, A., Bos, R., Gore, F. & Bartram, J. (2008). Safe Water, Better Health: Costs, Benefits and Sustainability of Interventions to Protect and Promote Health. *World Health Organization; Geneva, Switzerland*:
- Spears, D. & Haddad, L. J. (2015) The Power of WASH: Why Sanitation Matters for Nutrition. Global Food Policy Report, 19–23. *International Food Policy Research Institute, Washington, DC*.
- United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6, (2015): Ensure Availability and Sustainable Management of Water and Sanitation for All. *Sustainable Development Goals KnowledgePlatform*. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg6>.
- World Bank Group. *World development report 2016: Digital dividends*. World Bank Publications, 176-184.
- World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2012). Water sanitation and hygiene (online). World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/monitoring/jmp2012/fast_facts/en/
- World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2014). Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation (JMP). Progress on drinking water and sanitation. ISBN 9789241507240.
- World Health Organization, (2015) Child Growth Standards: Length/height for Age. World Health Organization, Geneva. www.who.int/childgrowth/standards.

World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2017). Progress on Drinking Water, Sanitation and Hygiene: Update and SDG Baselines, Geneva: World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF).

World Health Organization/United Nations Children's Fund, (2015). Water, sanitation and hygiene in health care facilities: Status in low- and middle-income countries and way forward. Geneva: WHO. Retrieved from http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/publications/wash-health-care-facilities/en/